

A STUDY ON THE RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS WITH A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES (TCS)

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Abstract: *Human resource management is one of the most crucial aspects of any business. Employees are an organization's strength, so it's critical to manage them well. However, prior to management, it is critical to select the most qualified and deserving people for the firm. Because organizational and individual growth can be quantified, choosing the right applicant for the right job is critical. The process of discovering and preparing potential individuals to apply for positions is referred to as recruitment. With its method of recruiting as many applications as possible for empty jobs, recruitment is referred to as a positive process. The process of picking the best qualified candidates for open positions is referred to as selection. Selection is referred to as a negative process since it involves the elimination or rejection of as many applications as possible in order to select the best candidate for the job. TCS assesses employees based on their attitude and, of course, their technical and professional skills. The study focuses on determining the effectiveness of the recruitment selection process and, as a result, analyzing the selection and recruiting procedure.*

Keywords: *Employees, Management, Recruitment, Selection, Process, Tata Consultancy Services*

Introduction

Human Resource Management (HRM) had its humble beginnings in western countries in the 1930s. The concept of human resource management was developed in ancient literatures in general and in Indian philosophy in particular. The fundamental goal of HRM was to inspire and motivate employees to recognize their strengths and put them to good use. HRM's key goal is to determine not just an individual employee's existing potential, but also his inherent abilities. HRD attempts to help employees develop as individuals by bringing forth their hidden potentials. An organization's most valuable resource is its human resources. The quality of the individuals who work in every organization determines whether it succeeds or fails. Hiring is not the same as recruiting.

Human resource management is concerned with the management of people inside organizations and focuses on policies and procedures. Selection and Employment Before selecting acceptable candidates for jobs, the strategy of drawing them to the firm. Recruitment is just one step in the overall hiring process. His selection procedure begins with

gathering all of the applicant's information from his application form and concludes with the candidate's induction into the organization progress. Selection is the process of separating candidates in order to find and hire those who have a better chance of succeeding in a position. Employees are an organization's strength, hence every organization requires a well-qualified employee. As a result, it is critical to effectively manage them. To retain employees, TCS caters to their objectives, inspiring them to reach their full potential and providing them with a clear roadmap and required tools for personal success. TCS provides end-to-end solutions and strategic planning using the Think-Build-Operate process.

Company Profile

Tata Consultancy Services Limited (TCS) is a global leader in information technology consulting, services, and business process outsourcing. TCS envisioned and pioneered the flexible global business practice that allows firms to function more efficiently and deliver more value today. They began operations in 1968, when the IT services industry as we know it did not exist. They are currently one of the world's major information technology firms, with a presence in 34 countries on six continents and a comprehensive array of services across a wide range of companies. Our valued customers include seven Fortune 500 firms.

They are part of the TATA group, one of Asia's greatest conglomerates, which, with its interests in energy, telecommunications, financial services, chemicals, engineering, and materials, gives us a solid understanding of the specific business difficulties that global firms face. As we go into an era of e-business, where IT professionals will interview employers so thoroughly that 40% of companies will fail their recruitment targets, HR's position will take on unimaginable proportions and will be subjected to enormous obstacles. How has TCS risen to and maintained its number one position with this sensitive breed of IT professionals is a subject that market observers have pondered a thousand times. There is just one answer: a strong desire for excellence in workplace operations.

In a setting that defines traditional roles and responsibilities, TCS has created an unbreakable link with strong HR practices. The TCRS - HR group collaborates with technological professionals to achieve an enviable synergy. HR's position, which is ostensibly that of a facilitator. HR is the spark that launches and institutionalizes processes, whether it's recruitment or career development. It's a huge undertaking to manage all of the functions for almost 14000 personnel, yet the smoothness of the operation is fascinating. The solution is an HR framework that allows for flexibility and empowerment.

According to S Padmanabhan, executive vice president, worldwide human resources, "a bad performer is not inevitably a terrible performer for life." TCS stands for Tata Consultancy Services. The information technology behemoth employs 45,000 people and is valued at Rs 9,749 crore. Nearly 9% of the company's revenue comes from outside India. And the majority of its employees work in 34 TCS offices across the world and on-site in more than 50 countries. When a project changes, the supervisor for the majority of them changes as well. Given the fact that no two projects or, for that matter, managers are alike, performance management and appraisal must be a nightmare.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To obtain a better understanding of the TCS recruiting and selection process
- To examine TCS's Recruitment and Selection procedure.

Review of Literature

Men (2015), came to the conclusion that employee engagement is linked to a variety of other outcomes in employee-activity relationships, and that it is involuntary due to organizational contextual characteristics such as unassailable leadership and open interaction. The straightforward and tortuous personalities of dependable leading and straight connection on striking were examined in this study. Quality employee-organization interactions have a good impact on the work plant that is meshing (i.e. employee combine, discipline, mutuality, message and satisfaction).

Turner (2010), claims that an organization's success is determined by its ability to get the appropriate people in the right location at the right time.

According to Sizler (2010), the hiring process does not finish when a candidate submits an application and selection of appropriate applicants, but also includes sustaining and retaining the selected employees.

Jackson et al. and Bratton and Gold (2009), Human resource management approaches in any business organisation are developed to meet corporate objectives and materialisation of strategic plans through training and development of personnel, with the ultimate goal of improving organisational performance and profits, as discussed by Jackson et al. (2009). The situation of the labour market and a firm's strength within it determine the type of recruiting and selection for an HRM approach company. Furthermore, such businesses must keep track of how the situation of the labour market relates to potential hires through the projection of an

image that will influence and reinforce candidate expectations.

According to Costello (2006), "The set of activities and processes needed to lawfully acquire a sufficient number of qualified persons," at the correct place and time so that people and organizations can choose each other in their own best immediate and long-term activities"

Research Methodology

This research is a combination of exploratory and descriptive research. The purpose of this research was to learn more about TCS' recruitment and selection procedures. It's also descriptive research because a major examination of the TCS recruitment and selection process was conducted.

Primary and secondary data from various sources are used in the analysis and interpretation. The purpose of this study is to look into the TCS employee recruiting and selection process. This research is supported by data. The primary data was acquired directly from the sample respondents using a Google form and a questionnaire method. For this study, the questionnaire method was used. A questionnaire was created in order to make the survey procedure more efficient. The secondary data for this study was gathered from relevant published papers and literature. Secondary data is gathered from a variety of sources, including research reports, TCS websites, books and publications, research papers published in online journals, and web details. The data was transcribed into tables, and I used the Percentage approach & Chi square test for effective analyzing purposes, using the Linkert scale method as a base.

Sample Design

The sample respondent should be represented in the Population. In this study, 50 employees were surveyed in order to get better understanding and assess the TCS recruitment and selection process and method. On the basis of convenience sampling, the real respondents were contacted.

Recruitment & Selection Process In TCS

Recruitment is the process by which businesses find and recruit people to fill employment openings. Most businesses need to hire new personnel on a regular basis to replace those who leave or are promoted, in order to acquire new skills and foster organizational growth. "A procedure to identify the sources of manpower to satisfy the requirement of the staffing schedule and to utilize effective strategies for attracting the manpower in sufficient numbers to permit effective selection of an efficient workforce," according to the definition of recruitment.

Recruitment is a "linking function," bringing together those who need jobs and those who are looking for work. It's a 'joining procedure' in that it brings job searchers and employers together with the goal of encouraging the former to apply for a position with the latter. The organization must communicate the position in such a way that job seekers respond in order to attract candidates for the positions. To be cost-effective, the hiring process should attract eligible applicants while also providing enough information for unqualified individuals to self-select. As a result, the recruitment process begins with the search for new recruits and ends with the submission of their applications. As a result, a pool of applicants is created from whom new employees are chosen.

Selection refers to the process of selecting or selecting suitable candidates by first requesting and obtaining helpful information about the individual. The organization strives to locate potential employees and encourages them to apply for vacancies at various levels through the recruitment process. As a result, recruiting creates a pool of candidates from whom to choose. Selection is the process of selecting people with the appropriate qualifications to fill roles in an organization. The primary purpose is to choose the best applicant from a pool of qualified individuals who can accomplish the job well. The purpose of selection is to find the most qualified candidate who will best meet a company's employment criteria, as well as to determine which job applicant will be successful if hired. To achieve this purpose, the organization collects and evaluates information about applicants in terms of age, credentials, skills, experience, and other factors, and the job requirements are matched with candidate profiles. After eliminating the unfit applicants through consecutive stages of the selection process, the most suited person is chosen. The amount and quality of labor performed by employees is directly affected by how well they are matched to their jobs.

Sources of Recruitment & Selection Process In TCS

The ways of recruiting people that are most regularly employed are listed below.

Internal Methods

This refers to the process of filling job openings from within the company. Instead of hiring someone from the outside, existing staff are chosen. A company may conclude that the proper individuals with the right capabilities for the job are available, especially if its training and development programme has been successful.

- Transfers and promotions

This is a method of internally filling vacancies through transfers and promotions. A transfer is a lateral movement from one job to another within the same grade. It may result in shifts in

industries and responsibilities, as well as working conditions and other factors, although not always in pay. Promotion entails an employee moving from a lower to a higher level position, which is accompanied by changes in duties, responsibilities, status, and worth.

- Job Posting

Another option to hire employees from within is to publicize job openings. The firm uses this strategy to advertise job openings on bulletin boards, the internet, and other comparable channels. One of the major advantages of this strategy is that it allows highly qualified employees to explore for opportunities for advancement inside the organization.

- Employee referrals

The term "employee referral" refers to the use of personal relationships to identify job openings. It is a recommendation for a job candidate from a current employee. Employees in the organization are encouraged to recommend the names of their friends who work in other organizations for a possible future vacancy. In reality, in today's highly competitive sector, this has become a common means of hiring employees. Employees whose recommendations are approved are rewarded handsomely by their employers.

External Methods

This refers to hiring people from outside the company to fill employment openings. Most businesses, especially those that are rapidly growing or operate in industries with high personnel turnover, engage in external recruitment on a regular basis.

- Recruitment on campus

It is a form of recruitment that involves going to college campuses and placement centres. Recruiters go to a reputable educational institution to look for job seekers with the necessary technical or professional abilities. Information about the positions and recruiters is offered to job seekers. A preliminary screening is conducted on campus, and those who are shortlisted are subsequently subjected to the process reminder. If campus recruitment is employed, the human resources department should take steps to ensure that recruiters are informed about the positions that need to be filled in the organization and that they apply good interviewing techniques.

- Advertisements

Advertisements in newspapers, trade, professional, and technical publications, radio, and television are only a few examples. This strategy is appropriate when an organization wants to reach a big target population and needs a reasonably significant number of talented

individuals who are geographically dispersed.

- Employment Service Providers

These companies specialize in the recruitment and selection of candidates. They frequently specialize in hiring for specific industries. They usually produce a candidate shortlist based on the persons who have registered with the agency. They also provide temporary or interim workers.

- Consultancy services for hiring
- Companies entrust their workforce needs to placement and recruiting consultants, who are in charge of finding acceptable individuals for the corporation.
- Walk-ins / Unsolicited Applicants

Generally, companies receive unsolicited applications based on varied economic conditions, the company's image, and the job seeker's assessment of the types of employment that might be offered, and so on. Such applications are usually stored in a database, and when a relevant opening emerges, the company will contact the candidates to invite them to apply through a formal route.

- Third party

Third-party sources include commercial or private job agencies, state agencies, and placement offices of schools, universities, and professional associations, as well as recruiting businesses, management consulting firms, indoctrination seminars for college teachers, and friends and relatives. The most often used sources are private employment agencies. They charge the applicant a modest fee. General office help, salesman, technical workers, accountants, computer employees, engineers, and executives are just a few of the occupations they specialise in. Professional organisations or recruiting businesses keep detailed records of all employed executives. These companies keep detailed records on all of the executives that work for them. Organizations that lose money regard these corporations as "head hunters," "raiders," and "pirates" through the efforts of their personnel

Levels of Recruitment & Selection Process In TCS

Work Force Level

The work force level is the first level of any organisation; here, the chosen worker does the task that their boss has allocated to them. The initial employment at TCS is mostly concerned with software development, but it may also be hardware or networking related, therefore the candidate should be familiar with computer languages, hardware, and

networking for the position for which he or she is trying to apply. Currently, the labour force recruitment procedure is underway. 1. Application: candidates can apply online or respond to one of the company's advertisements. They screen resumes and contact them for an interview. The procedure for selection is as follows: 1) Written (Aptitude test) 2) Perform an interview (Technical & non-technical) 3) Problem-solving in groups

Frontline Level

The frontline level is the highest level of the labor force. A person could be in charge of a single team of workers. It is here that strong technical as well as communication skills are required. It is a two-way communication process in which he communicates with both his labour force and his technical department. This is an internal and external process in which employees are chosen from within and outside the firm. The selection process on the inside differs from that on the exterior. The process of hiring frontline employees from outside the organisation is now underway. 1) Textual 2) Perform an interview (technical & non-technical) 3) Analysis of case studies and aptitude tests 4) Discussion in groups

They take into account internal choices.

1. As per their performance
2. Schedule an interview
3. Leadership potential

Middle Management Level

The Executive Selection Scheme is a fast-track programme for high-potential professionals who want to advance quickly. It is in charge of all of the company's projects. This is a two-way communication system as well. Here, the manager communicates with his high-ranking officials, lower-level employees, and clients. The middle management level selection procedure is in underway. This is dependent on both internal and external factors.

- Internal Method
 1. An interview
 2. A presentation
 3. An analysis of a case study
 4. Quality of leadership
 5. According to their performance
- External Method
 1. Written aptitude test
 2. Technical and non-technical interviews
 3. Case study analysis
 4. Presentation
 5. Ability to lead
 6. Negotiation

Top Management Level

It is the highest and most prominent position in the Tata Consultancy Service, comparable to CEO and MD. Here, the top most individual is mostly concerned with managing the entire firm; they also develop plans connected to phosphorus decision-making in the near future. Top-level management is in charge of the organization's goals and policies, as well as its ultimate source of authority. They coordinate the various departments of the company, including their budgets, procedures, and agendas, and provide control and coordination to all of the firm's activities. The performance of the firm is held accountable by top-level management to the shareholders. There is no external recruitment process Interview

1. Presentation of the Candidate
2. Offers and bargaining.

Findings

- TCS has 60% IT personnel and 40% non-IT employees, and their preferred candidates are mostly fresher's.
- Casual applicants have a 48 percent chance of getting hired at TCS, and they can contact them via phone or email.
- The organization uses internal recruitment sources to hire fresh people, both directly and through job boards, which is beneficial to the company.
- TCS recruits mostly through campus recruiting and the TCS Nqt exam.
- According to the results of the study, 45 respondents are satisfied with TCS's selection procedure, and the company's overall selection strategy is good.
- In order to save time and hire productive employees, the best screening method is done prior to recruiting.
- TCS's recruitment procedure is too lengthy, yet they take a positive approach throughout it.
- TCS's selection policy states that age has no impact on the company's employee selection process.
- TCS's selection policy states that there is no link between gender and the employee selection process.

Suggestion

TCS's recruitment procedures have been found to be satisfactory on the whole. It is recommended that the organization continue to follow its current recruitment and selection

policies in the future. It is proposed that in order to find the desired and required employees, the organization should give equal weight to external sources such as agencies, references, and so on. It is proposed that the organization should support freshmen as well as experienced candidates based on their skills. It can improve and implement more cutting-edge strategies for recruiting potential personnel. We may conclude from the study results that the organization's recruitment and selection process is excellent.

Conclusion

Recruitment and selection processes play a vital role in every organization. According to the research, TCS's recruitment method is extremely effective. The HR manager of the chosen organization must concentrate on selecting the right people from other sources such as campus interviews, sourcing, walk-ins, consulting, and so on. The recruitment and selection process is carried out by evaluating the candidates' skills, knowledge, and abilities that are highly required for the open positions in the organization. The recruitment process informs qualified candidates about job openings and promotes the company's reputation. Give sufficient information about the jobs so that applicants may compare their qualifications and interests, and produce a pool of the top prospects who will apply for the open positions. Recruitment is a company's first point of contact with potential employees.

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